

Universal and Reproducible Compute

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Universal and Reproducible Compute?

Universal = Runs everywhere
Reproducible = Runs the same*

* (for some definitions of "same")

Who Is This Guy?

Google

 Microsoft

amazon

 kubernetes

 Kubeflow

 CHEF™

Google

kubernetes

Microsoft

Kubeflow

amazon

CHEF™

How Things Have Changed...

Then:

```
ftp://files.nia.nih.gov/studies/2005_05_PET_data/smith_jane_003.tgz
```

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```
ftp://files.nia.nih.gov/studies/2005_05_PET_data/smith_jane_003.tgz
```

Now:

```
https://noaa-nexrad.s3.amazonaws.com/2015/08/08/KARX20150808_003_V06.gz
```

But It Works?

Does it?

```
https://noaa-nexrad.s3.amazonaws.com/2015/08/08/KARX20150808_003_V06.gz
```

Security :(

Self Managed

Commercial

Metadata
in the URL

Non-deterministic

AND

We Couldn't Keep Up Even If We Wanted To!

175 zettabytes of data stored

Data Growing Rapidly

42% y/y growth in enterprise data
60% of companies have 1PB+
57% of enterprise data is outside traditional data centers

Moving it is slow and expensive

45% excess growth rate of data compared to bandwidth (2010-2020)
1.8B years to move the datasphere at current bandwidth

Approx. 100% is under governance

\$250B governance fines since 2008
67,000 regulations worldwide
HIPAA, GDPR, GLBA, FISMA, NIST, MARS-E, IRS-1075, CCPA, POI, PCI-DSS, etc.

AND

Reproducibility is NOT just About Data!

- What code (and dependencies, drivers, etc) did you use?
- Is the stack still available?
- Who can examine the (whole) process?
- Where do you write the metadata, logs, etc for searching (and in what format)?

How Can We Address It?

Portugal

Compute Over Data

Compute Over Data

Bacalhau

Build It Yourself?

Building It Yourself?

Data Scientist

Developer

I can build it!

Building It Yourself

I'd like to run some data analysis.

Custom
Orchestration
System™

Data Scientist

Developer

Building It Yourself

I'd like to run some analysis outside my core data center, please.

aws

Custom
Orchestration
System™

Data
Scientist

Google Cloud

Developer

Building It

Customer
Orchestration
System

K, now I would like to:

- Schedule against data locality
- Run during using only green power
- Run in a single geo
- Collect audit logs
- Target spot workloads by price
- Use spare compute on existing devices
- Isolate jobs using a custom executor
- ...

Data Scientist

And I want to go on vacation!

Google Cloud

Building It Yourself?

Custom
Orchestration
System™

And I want to go on
vacation!

Developer

**Be
You?**

Build It With a Community

Solution: OSS Compute Over Data Platforms

OSS
Compute Over
Data Platform

Data
Scientist

Developer

Solution: OSS Compute Over Data Platforms

Data Scientist

Developer

Open Source & Extensible

Solution: OSS Compute Over Data Platforms

Data Scientist

Built for Multi-Cloud

Solution: OSS Compute Over Data Platforms

Data Scientist

Made for
Non-Data
Centers

Key Scenarios For Bacalhau

**Reproducible
Execution**

**Respecting
Data Gravity**

**Supports for
Isolation**

Bacalhau Job


```
Job:
  APIVersion: V1beta2
  Spec:
    EngineSpec:
      Params:
        EnvironmentVariables:
          - INPUTFILE=/var/log/logs_to_process/aperitivo_logs.log.1
          - QUERY=SELECT * FROM log_data WHERE message LIKE '%
[SECURITY]%' ORDER BY '@timestamp'
        Image: docker.io/bacalhauproject/motherduck-log-processor:1.1.6
        Type: docker
      Resources:
        GPU: ""
        Memory: 4gb
    Inputs:
      - Name: logs_to_process
        SourcePath: QmXoypizjW3WknFiJnKLwHCnL72vedxjQkDDP1mXWo6uco
        StorageSource: S3
        path: /var/log/logs_to_process
```

Parameterizable

Repeatable

**Data Aware
Scheduling**

Flexible Engine

New Forms Of Collaboration

Before Bacalhau

Insulated Jobs

Insulated Jobs

Org A

Ok, can I get
access to your
data?

Org B

Insulated Jobs

Org A

I'd love to, but:

Personal data shall be:

1. processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject ('lawfulness, fairness and transparency');
2. collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes; further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes shall, in accordance with [Article 89\(1\)](#), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes ('purpose limitation');
3. adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed ('data minimisation');
4. accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date; every reasonable step must be taken to ...

Org B

Insulated Jobs

Org A

Org B

The logo consists of three blue chevron-like shapes pointing right, with a small blue circle in the center of the middle shape.

With Bacalhau

Insulated Jobs

Org A

Org B

Ok, can I get access to your data?

Insulated Jobs

Org A

Org B

Insulated Jobs

Insulated Jobs

Org A

Let's ensure
this job is ok
to run.

Org B

Insulated Jobs

Org A

Org B

Insulated Jobs

Org A

Ok, Looks
Good*! ✓

*Not sensitive query

Org B

Insulated Jobs

Org A

Runs on Local
Machines

Against Local
Data

Org B

Insulated Jobs

Org A

Org B

Insulated Jobs

Org A

Let's audit the results.

Org B

Insulated Jobs

Org A

Org B

Insulated Jobs

Org A

Org B

Ok, Looks
Good*!

*Not sensitive result

With Bacalhau and Octostore

Secure & Audited Cross-Org Execution

Through Bacalhau & Octostore, every job is tracked and auditable

Org A

Org B

Metadata recorded:

- Who submitted the job
- What job was submitted
- Who audited the job
- What machine(s) the job ran on
- What data/dataset accessed
- What results were produced
- Who audited the results
- Who downloaded the results

Automatically!

Already In Use by the USN & USAF

U.S. Navy Chooses Bacalhau to Manage Predictive Maintenance Workloads

Introduction

In a lighthouse project that is adopting new technologies, the U.S. Navy chose Bacalhau open-source software, supported by Expanso, as an orchestration solution. Bacalhau software assists the U.S. Navy with their goal of deploying artificial intelligence capabilities in undersea operations. Working closely with our partner [Mycelial](#), Expanso addressed several obstacles to allow the use of AI-enabled analytics in the demanding and harsh conditions found in deep ocean environments. Bacalhau also was able to satisfy the U.S. Navy's stringent security standards, while making it possible to access data and computation over unreliable networks.

Community Roadmap!

- Bi-Weekly Community Calls
- Quarterly Workshops
- Monthly Newsletters
- #bacalhau Slack & social media

Thank You!

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(twitter, github, mastodon, etc)

Bacalhau - bacalhau.org

GitHub Repo

Slack

Google Group